

Genetic resources program

Rice germplasm collected from low-lying areas of Orissa

J. K. Roy, D. P. Ghorai, R. N. De, and A. Panda, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, India

As a part of the India-wide rice germplasm collection program formulated in 1978, CRRI surveyed and collected rice germplasm from the typical low-lying areas of

Orissa in 1978 kharif.

Although the germplasm in those areas in India is not threatened by immediate extinction (most current improved varieties are not suitable for such conditions), collection in such areas is being emphasized to locate donors for the development of improved varieties for flood-prone and waterlogged areas, which make up about a third of India's

total rice area.

The survey resulted in the collection of 140 typical low-lying varieties. Some varieties such as Rabana, Dhusara, Magura, Champeisali, Cuttack Chandi, and Ratnachudi are common in several blocks. All the varieties collected, including two scented types, were late maturing with coarse, fine, or very fine grain. They are being evaluated under waterlogged conditions in 1979 kharif. More than 15,000 viable accessions are now in the national germplasm collection at CRRI. ■

Grain quality

An X-ray technique to screen sun cracks in rice grains

R. C. Chaudhary and N. P. S. Kohli, Department of Plant Breeding, C. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

Sun cracks develop in mature rice grains exposed to variable humidity and temperature. Overmature crops left in the field or threshed grain left in the open are exposed to low temperature and humidity at night and high temperature and low humidity in daylight hours. The alternate soaking and drying lead to the "sun cracking" of the endosperm. The sun-cracked grains invariably break during hulling and milling. Other grains break independently of sun-cracking because of mechanical damage. When evaluating varieties for head-rice recovery, the broken kernels are separated after milling and expressed as a percentage of rough rice. But there has been no method to determine if sun-cracking or mechanical damage caused the breakage. Therefore head-rice recovery has been considered subjective and inheritance studies on the trait have been inconclusive.

An X-ray technique has been used to measure the degree of damage caused by sun cracks, thus allowing separate determination of breakage due to milling.

Grains with sun crack (white arrow) and mechanical damage (black arrow). Pantnagar, India.

An X-ray inspection unit (Faxitron model 804, 14 kV, current 2mA) was used. Rice samples suspected of high damage were spread on an X-ray plate 25 cm from the source. The samples were exposed for 3 seconds, then the plates

were developed by the usual method. The cracks and damage appeared in the plate clearly (see photo). Damaged grain can also be counted from positive plates. The technique may be useful to breeders in determining genotypic differences and